

GIBBS MEASURES FOR THE THREE-STATE SOS MODEL ON A CAYLEY TREE

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Annotatsiya. Biz Keli daraxtida uch holatli SOS (solid-on-solid) modelini qaraymiz. Biz har bir yechimi yagona Gibbs o‘lchovlariga mos keluvchi noxiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini yechish yordamida Gibbs o‘lchovlarini tavsiflaymiz. Bu model uchun turli xil Gibbs o‘lchovlari mavjudligini ta’minlaydigan parametrlarga nisbatan ba’zi shartlarni topamiz.

Аннотация. Мы рассматриваем модель SOS (solid-on-solid) с тремя состояниями на дереве Кэли. Мы описание мер Гиббса помощью методом решения системы нелинейных уравнений, каждому решению уравнения соответствует одна мера Гиббса. Находим такие условия на параметры, которые обеспечивают существование различных мер Гиббса для модели.

Abstract. We consider a three-state SOS (solid-on-solid) model on a Cayley tree. We reduce the description of Gibbs measures to solving the system of non-linear equations, which each solution of the equation corresponds to one Gibbs measure. We find some conditions on the parameters such that ensures the existence of different Gibbs measures for the model.

In this work, for the SOS model on Cayley trees we give a very wide class of new Gibbs measures.

In [2] for the Ising model on Cayley trees the existence of a very wide class of Gibbs measures is proved. It is also shown that these new measures are extreme under some conditions on the temperature.

Let $\Gamma^k = (V, L)$ be the uniform Cayley tree, where each vertex has $k+1$ neighbors with V being the set of vertices and L the set of edges (see [1]).

Let $\Phi := \{0, 1, 2, \dots, m\}$, $m \geq 1$, and the configuration $\sigma \in \Phi^V$, i.e., $\sigma = \{\sigma(x) \in \Phi : x \in V\}$.

The Hamiltonian of SOS model is defined by

$$H(\sigma) = -J \sum_{\langle x, y \rangle \in L} |\sigma(x) - \sigma(y)|, \quad (1)$$

where $J \in \mathbb{P}$ and $\langle x, y \rangle$ stands for nearest neighbor vertices.

Fix $x^0 \in V$. For $x, y \in V$ we will write $x < y$ if the path from x^0 to y passes through x . A vertex y is called a direct successor of x if $y > x$ and x, y are neighbors. Note that in Γ^k every vertex $x \neq x^0$ has k direct descendants, and x^0 has $k+1$ descendants.

Let $h : x \mapsto h_x = (h_{0,x}, h_{1,x}, \dots, h_{m,x}) \in \mathbb{P}^{m+1}$ be a vector function of $x \in V \setminus \{x^0\}$. Consider a probability distribution $\mu^{(n)}$ on Ω_{V_n} :

$$\mu^n(\sigma_n) = Z_n^{-1} \exp(-\beta H(\sigma_n) + \sum_{x \in W_n} h_{\sigma(x), x}), \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_n \in \Omega_{V_n}$ and $Z_n = \sum_{\tilde{\sigma}_n \in \Omega_{V_n}} \exp(-\beta H(\tilde{\sigma}_n) + \sum_{x \in W_n} h_{\tilde{\sigma}(x), x})$.

A probability distribution $\mu^{(n)}$ is said to be compatible if for any $n \geq 1$ and $\sigma_{n-1} \in \Omega_{V_{n-1}}$, we have

$$\sum_{\omega_n \in \Omega_{W_n}} \mu^{(n)}(\sigma_{n-1} \vee \omega_n) = \mu^{(n-1)}(\sigma_{n-1}), \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma_{n-1} \vee \omega_n \in \Omega_{V_n}$.

In this case, there is a unique measure μ on Ω such that

$$\mu(\{\sigma_{V_n} = \sigma_n\}) = \mu^{(n)}(\sigma_n)$$

for all n and $\sigma_n \in \Omega_{V_n}$. Such a measure is called an SGM corresponding to the Hamiltonian H and to the function $x \mapsto h_x$, $x \neq x_0$. The following statement gives a condition on h_x guaranteeing that the distribution of $\mu^{(n)}(\sigma_n)$ is compatible.

Theorem 1. [3] *The probability distributions $\mu^{(n)}(\sigma_n), n = 1, 2, \dots$ determined by the formula (2) are compatible iff for any $x \in V \setminus \{x^0\}$ the following equation holds,*

$$h_x^* = \sum_{y \in S(x)} F(h_y^*, m, \theta), \quad (4)$$

where $\theta = e^{J\beta}$, $\beta = \frac{1}{T}$. Here $h_x^* = (h_{0,x} - h_{m,x}, h_{1,x} - h_{m,x}, \dots, h_{m-1,x} - h_{m,x})$ and $F(\bullet, m, \theta) : \mathbb{P}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{P}^m$ is a vector function, i.e. $F(h, m, \theta) = (F_0((h, m, \theta)), \dots, F_{m-1}(h, m, \theta))$, $h = (h_0, h_1, \dots, h_{m-1})$, such that

$$F_i(h, m, \theta) = \ln \frac{\sum_{j=0}^{m-1} \theta^{i-j} e^{h_j} + \theta^{m-i}}{\sum_{j=0}^{m-1} \theta^{m-j} e^{h_j} + 1}, \quad i = 0, \dots, m-1. \quad (5)$$

The set of vertices of a Cayley tree of order k is denoted by V^k . For $x \in V$ by $S_{k_0}(x)$ we denote arbitrary k_0 vertices of the set $S(x)$. If on the vertex x we have $h_x = \bar{h}$, then to the vertex $S_a(x)$ we put the value $h_x = \bar{h}$, to the other vertices of $S_b(x)$ we put the value $h_x = \bar{l}$. If on the vertex x we have $h_x = \bar{l}$, then on the vertex $S_c(x)$ we put the value $h_x = \bar{h}$, on the remaining vertices of $S_s(x)$ we put $h_x = \bar{l}$. Note that $a + b = k, c + s = k$. Using this construction, for $\bar{h} = (0, h_2)$ and $\bar{l} = (0, l_2)$ due to Theorem 1 we have

$$\begin{cases} h_2 = af(h_2) + bf(l_2) \\ l_2 = cf(h_2) + sf(l_2) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where $f(x) = \ln \frac{\exp(x) + 2\theta}{\theta^2 + \theta \exp(x) + 1}$.

Let $b \neq 0$, $\varphi(x) = \frac{1}{b}((bc - as) f_\theta(x) + sx)$ and $\psi(x) = af_\theta(x) + bf_\theta\left(\frac{1}{b}((bc - as) f_\theta(x) + sx)\right)$.

Note that the function $\psi(x)$ is continuous and bounded. This implies that it has at least a fixed point, say, x^* .

Theorem 2. *Let $b \neq 0$. If the condition $|\psi'(x^*)| > 1$ is satisfied, then for the SOS model there exist at least three Gibbs measures, which correspond to the solutions of the system of equation (6).*

REFERENCES

1. U.A. Rozikov, *Gibbs Measures on Cayley Trees*, World Scientific, Singapore, 2013.
2. M.M. Rahmatullaev, U.A.Rozikov, Ising model on Cayley trees: a new class of Gibbs measures and their comparison with known ones. *J.Stat.Mech.* 2017, pp.2-15.
3. Rozikov U.A. Suhov Y.M. Gibbs measures for SOS model on a Cayley tree. *Inf.Dim.An.,Quant. Prob. and Related Topics.* 2006, V9, N3, 471-488.